

The Tomb of Sunan Kalijaga: Kadilangu Village, Demak Regency (Central Java)

also known as “Makam Sunan Kalijaga: Desa Kadilangu, Kabupaten Demak (Propinsi Jawa Tengah)”

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Islamic Traditions, Southeast Asian Religions, Religious Place, Sufi, Tomb

Sunan Kalijaga (1450-1513)—also known as Raden Said or Lokajaya in his earlier life—is the most celebrated saint among the Wali Songo. Wali Songo collectively refers to nine saints who contributed to the spread of Islam in Java, according to the eighteenth-century Javanese historical tradition that is reflected in various versions of the Babad Tanah Jawi. Born into a Majapahit noble family in Tuban, Raden Said was addicted to gambling and smoking opium. The profligate youth went on to become a notorious highwayman. But when the young man attempted to prey upon the passing Sunan Bonang, his life trajectory changed drastically. Inspired by the magical powers of Sunan Bonang, Raden Said left behind his life of crime. The youth then became Sunan Bonang's star disciple. After several trials, notably his long watch (Javanese: jaga) over the river Kali, Raden Said earned the appellation of Sunan Kalijaga. There is a general consensus amongst historians and anthropologists that Sunan Kalijaga is remembered for his humanity: his distinctive Javanese-ness, a devout Muslim and extensive use of wayang kulit (shadow puppetry) in the dakwah strategy (act of inviting people to embrace Islam). He is also remembered for lending credibility to the newly-established Mataram Sultanate. According to a legend mentioned in the Babad Tanah Jawi, sometime during the 1470s—when the Wali Songo were busy building the Grand Mosque at Demak in a single day—they were unable to agree on the orientation of the building. Muslims are obligated to pray five times a day facing Mecca towards the Ka'aba. Therefore, mosques are oriented towards the Ka'aba. The Babad Jaka Tangkir chronicle tells us that the structure built by the Wali Songo was not easily brought into alignment with Ka'bah, the material-spiritual center of Islam. The deferral of the settlement of the kéblat (Javanese: to face Mecca/obey) of the Grand Mosque of Demak— as recorded by Javanese historical tradition—highlights the complex process of balancing between traditional customs and Islam. Sunan Kalijaga's miraculous manipulation of both the Meccan Ka'aba and the Grand Mosque at Demak illustrates the alignment of Islam with Javanese tradition. The Sunan Kalijaga Mosque at Kadilangu, Demak—adjacent to the tomb of Sunan Kalijaga [not to be confused with the Grand Mosque at Demak]—adopted local features of mosque construction. For example, the tiered roof instead of the Moorish-style dome and minaret. The latter style was introduced as an element of mosque construction at the turn of the twentieth century.

Date Range: 1513 CE - 2022 CE

Region: Java

Region tags: Southeast Asia, Indonesia, Java

The shaded region highlights the tomb of Sunan Kalijaga, situated in the desa (village) of Kadilangu, located about a mile away from the Grand Mosque of Demak (Masjid Agung Demak).

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: W.L. Olthof, *Babad Tanah Jawi in Proza: Javaansche Geschiedenis* (Gravenhage: M. Nijhoff, 1941).

Notes: In his earlier life, Sunan Kalijaga was known as Raden Said. The son of a Majapahit duke from Tuban, Raden Said's youth was characterized by indulgence. After sustaining losses due to gambling, he became a highway bandit. He attempted to rob Sunan Bonang, his would-be mentor at Djati Sekar forest but failed. After Raden Said repented for his evil deeds, he undertook penance for two years and was mentored by Sunan Bonang. Near Cirebon, he once again engaged in ascetic practices on the banks of river called Jaga and became famous as Sunan Kalijaga.

— Source 1: Theodore G. Th Pigeaud and H.J. de Graaf, *Islamic States in Java, 1500-1700: A Summary, Bibliography and Index* (Dordrecht: Springer, 1976).

— Source 2: James J. Fox, "Sunan Kalijaga and the Rise of Mataram A Reading of the Babad Tanah Jawi as a Genealogical Narrative," in *Islam: Essays on Scripture, Thought and Society*, Street and Peter Riddell edited (Leiden: Brill, 1997), 187-218.

— Source 1: Jeyamalar Kathirithamby-Wells, " The Islamic City: Melaka to Jogjakarta, c. 1500-1800," *Modern Asian Studies* 20, no. 2 (1986): 333-51.

— Source 2: Hee Sook Lee-Niinioja, *Javanese Mosque Mirhabs and Syncretic Islamic Ornament* (Helsinki: Novel and Noble Communications, 2018).

— Source 3: Supatmo, "Perwujudan Estetis Seni Ornamen Masjid Peninggalan Walisanga di Jawa Tengah," *Jurnal Imaginasi* 11, no. 2 (2017).

— Source 1: Achmad Chodjim, *Mistik dan Makrifat: Sunan Kalijaga* (Jakarta: PT Serambi Ilmu Semesta, 2003).

— Source 2: Agus Sunyoto, *Atlas Wali Songo: Buku Pratama yang Mengungkap Wali Songo Sebagai Fakta Sejarah* (Bandung: Pustaka IIMaN dan Lesbumi PBNU, 2017).

Notes: Achmad Chodjim's " Mistik dan Makrifat: Sunan Kalijaga," provides a hagiographical account of Sunan Kalijaga. In *Atlas Wali Songo*, Agus Sunyoto provides a richly-empirical account of the life of Sunan Kalijaga. Sunan Kalijaga used Javanese puppetry (wayang kulit) in the furtherance of dakwah (invitation to the people to embrace Islam). In the wayang play *Dewa Ruci*, Sunan Kalijaga describes the character of Bhima (from the Hindu epic *Mahabharata*). Bhima meets with Dewa Ruci who is as big as a thumb but Bhima can enter the body of the latter. Soon after, Bhima witnesses revelation of spiritual experience. Through the performance of the *Dewa Ruci* play, Sunan Kalijaga tells his students that the spiritual figure of Dewa Ruci is actually al- Khidr from the Quran who would be meeting the students during the course of their spiritual journey.

— Source 1: Nancy Florida, *Writing the Past, Inscribing the Future: History as Prophecy in Colonial Java* (Durham and London: Duke University Press, 1995).

— Source 2: George Quinn, *Bandit Saints of Java: How Java's Eccentric Saints are Challenging Fundamentalist Islam in Modern Indonesia* (Burrough on the Hill, Leices.: Monsoon Books, 2019).

— Source 3: Ermita Soenarto, " From Saints to Superheroes: The Wali Songo Myth in Contemporary

Indonesia's Popular Genres," *The Malaysian Branch of the Royal Asiatic Society* 78, no. 2 (2005): 33-82.

– Source 1: Clifford Geertz, *The Religion of Java* (New York: Free Press, 1960).

– Source 2: Mark Woodward, *Java, Indonesia and Islam* (Dordrecht: Springer, 2010).

– Source 3: Michael Laffan, *The Makings of Indonesian Islam: Orientalism and the Making of a Sufi Past* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2011).

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <http://resolver.kb.nl/resolve?urn=MMKB14:001592001:pdf>

– Source 1 Description: Bataviaasch Genootschap van Kunsten en Wetenschappen, *Rapporten Commissie in Nederlandsch Indie voor Oudheidkundig Onderzoek op Java en Madoera, 1905-6* (Batavia en Gravenhage: Albrecht and Co. en M. Nijhoff, 1907).

– Source 2 URL: <https://resolver.kb.nl/resolve?urn=MMKB21:043834000:pdf>

– Source 2 Description: J.J. Meinsma, *Babad Tanah Djawi in Proza: Javaansche Geschiedenis* (Gravenhage: Martinus Nijhoff, 1903).

– Source 3 URL: https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004454170_019

– Source 3 Description: J.J. Ras, "The Babad Tanah Jawi and its Reliability: Questions of Content, Structure and Function," in *The Babad Tanah Jawi and its Reliability: Questions of Content, Structure and Function*, C.D. Grijns and S.O. Robson edited (Leiden: KITLV, 1986), 246-73.

Notes: The bilingual document published in Dutch and Javanese (1907) titled "Rapporten Commissie in Nederlandsch Indie voor Oudheidkundig Onderzoek op Java en Madoera, 1905-6," unearths the use of parables by Sunan Kalijaga in his teachings. J.J. Meinsma's version of *Babad Tanah Jawi* (1903) is bilingual: in Dutch and Javanese (Kawi script). Meinsma's version of the *Babad Tanah Jawi* notes Ngadilangoe (Kadilangu) as the location of Sunan Kalijaga's tomb.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Body of water (as distinct from source)

– Other [specify]: None.

Notes: A pool of water adjacent to the Kadilangu mosque where pilgrims perform their ritual ablutions (wuduh) before entering the shrine.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– No

Notes: The place is located in the village of Kadilangu, about a mile from the Demak Grand Mosque and the district headquarters.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Notes: Kailangu, a coastal town is situated two kilometers to the Southeast of Demak amidst paddy fields.

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Field doesn't know

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

- ↳ One single feature
 - Other [specify]: Not applicable. The Mosque of Sunan Kalijaga at Kadilangu is adjacent to the mausoleum of Sunan Kalijaga.

- ↳ A group of structures:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ A group of features:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The Mosque of Sunan Kalijaga at Kadilangu and the mausoleum of Sunan Kalijaga are located adjacent to each other in Kadilangu village. The village is situated about a mile from the Grand Mosque of Demak that was according to the Babad Tanah Jawi built by the Wali Songo.

- ↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:
 - Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function
 - Worship
 - ↳ Worship:
 - Communal

- ↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

Notes: The Kadilangu mosque was a posthumous addition (1564). Sunan Kalijaga had built a small prayer hall or langgar during his lifetime. The Kadilangu mosque was subsequently renovated during the colonial era, and in the postcolonial period (1970 and 1990). For details see Ashadi (2017).

↳ In antiquity

– Once

Reference: Ashadi, Ashadi. *Makna Sinkretisme Bentuk Pada Arsitektur Mesjid-mesjid Walisanga*. Penerbit Arsitektur UMJ Press, 2017.

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Sunan Kalijaga

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Notes: Built by Pangeran Wijil. Pangeran is a title bestowed by the Sultan of Demak to the descendants of Sunan Kalijaga.

↳ Specify

– Religious specialists affiliated with political entity

– Private individual

– Other [specify]: Pangeran Wijil. Pangeran was a title bestowed on Sunan Kalijaga's descendants by the Sultan of Demak and continued sometime until the colonial period ~1880.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: The death of Sunan Kalijaga.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– No

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Sand

– Field doesn't know

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Plaster
– Field doesn't know

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: Not known

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Three-necked Mustaka (crown) of the mosque is built of metal. The lower part of the mirhab is tiled.

– Yes [specify]: Overall architecture of the Sunan Kalijaga Mosque at Kadilangu

Notes: The Kadilangu mosque is situated to the east of the tomb of Sunan Kalijaga. The roof of the mosque is influenced by Javanese roof architecture: three overlapping roofs. The mustaka (crown) is made of metal and is shaped like a stylized lotus motif (padma) The mustaka is situated above the overlapping roof structure. Above the mosque's main door, vine-patterned ornamentation surrounded by rows of floral motifs. The cupola contains an Arabic inscription that is undecipherable. The Kadilangu mosque embodies features of Javanese mosque architecture that include: (a) a square plan; (b) four soko guru (wooden pillars) that support the roof that lacks ornamentation; (c) mirhab, a niche in the wall containing the kiblat or the direction to Mecca; and, (d) ornamentation of the wooden pulpit. The ceiling has a number of chandeliers. The mosque stands in an open space, independent of the tomb of Sunan Kalijaga. The latter is situated in a walled compound.

– Yes [specify]: Details related to the Mausoleum of Sunan Kalijaga, Kadilangu

Notes: The tomb of Sunan Kalijaga is situated in a walled compound. Apart from the tomb of Sunan Kalijaga, the complex also includes the graves of Sunan Kalijaga's wife, children, sister, and father. The tomb building of Sunan Kalijaga is painted in cinnamon-blue (Javanese: wulung), the saint's favorite color. The wulung color is a signifier of the saint's popularity among the Javanese. The grave of Sunan Kalijaga is elevated compared to other graves in the mausoleum. The tomb of Sunan Kalijaga is undecorated. Adamite stone is used for the construction of the saint's tomb. The headstone does not include any inscription. Inside the tomb building, sheltered by a cupola, the saint lies under a 240 cm long, 100 cm wide and 100 cm high ledger. The cupola is supported by wooden walls. Within the building, heirlooms belonging to Sunan Kalijaga including the Kyai Kris Carubuk (a Javanese dagger) are stored.

Reference: Sangadah, Zuhrotus. Managemen Yayasan Sunan Kalijaga Kadilanga Demak Dalam Mengelola Wisata Religi. Semarang: Universitas Islam Negeri, 2015.
<http://eprints.walisongo.ac.id/id/eprint/4763/>.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

Notes: The mirhab is a niche in the wall containing the kiblāt, the direction to Mecca. The mirhab of Masjid Sunan Kalijaga, Kadilangu contains a carving of Kala Makara (inspired by Hindu-Buddhist art). The Kala Makara is a feature of early Javanese-Islamic art. The Kala Makara in the context of the Mosque at Kadilangu represents a Chinese flame. The upper part of the mirhab is painted white, the lower part painted with pink-colored tiles.

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Reference: Balai Pelestarian Cagar Budaya Jawa Tengah. "Fakta Tentang Masjid Dan Makam Sunan Kalijaga Kadilangu". Balai Pelestarian Cagar Budaya Jawa Tengah, n.d.. <http://kebudayaan.kemdikbud.go.id/bpcbjateng/fakta-tentang-masjid-dan-makam-sunan-kalijaga-kadilangu/>.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The peak of the roof (mustaka) is cast out of metal and is lotus-shaped.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

Notes: The inscription on the cupola in Arabic is indistinct.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: Inscription in Javanese decorates the porch of Masjid Kadilangu.

Notes: The inscription in Javanese reads, "puniko titimangsa ngadegipun masjid Kadilangu dinten ahad wage tanggal 16 sasi dulkijah tahun hijriyah alip tahun 1456." The year the mosque at Kadilangu was constructed. The inscription is declarative.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: The four soko guru that support the mosque roof signifies the relationship between humankind and God.

↳ Humans

– No

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Notes: Veneration of the saint is the appropriate expression.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: offerings of petals and small denominations of Indonesian currency.

↳ Personal effects:

– No

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– No

↳ Other

– Field doesn't know

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: Javanese customary tomb visitation or ziarah is intended to seek favors of the saint (Javanese: ngalap berkah).

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Through divination practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: The juru kunci or key-keeper of the shrine acts as the intermediary between the saint and the pilgrim.

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

- ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
- ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - Yes
- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: Field does not know.

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Libations:

– No

↳ Offerings of food:

– Yes [specify]: Tumpeng (yellow rice in the form of a cone representing Mount Merapi) offered on Idul Adha to pilgrims undertaking ziarah.

↳ Animal sacrifice:

– Yes [specify]: On Idul Adha. Performed at Masjid Sunan Kalijaga Kadilangu.

↳ Human sacrifice:

– No

↳ Sacred objects:

– No

↳ Daily life objects:

– Yes [specify]: Small denominations of Indonesian currency left at the donation box.

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: Field does not know.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: See the section below on rituals and performance.

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: On Idul Adha, animal sacrifice (involving the sacrificial slaughter of cattle and goats) at Masjid Sunan Kalijaga, Kadilangu.

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

Notes: Customary to offer cash at the donation box to seek the saint's intercession or a favor (ngalap berkah). For details see Quinn (2019).

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: Small denominations of cash.

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– No

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: See section below.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– Yes

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: The juru kunci or the key-keeper of the shrine, the descendants of Sunan Kalijaga.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: The shrine has been renovated periodically. The last renovation took place in the early 2000s.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Refer to the section below on Institutions and Scriptures on Yayasan Sunan Kalijaga (established in 1963) that is in-charge of shrine maintenance.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

Notes: Pilgrimage to the mausoleum of Sunan Kalijaga, as with the shrines of other Wali Songo saints is customary (ziarah). The tomb of Sunan Kalijaga is owned by his descendants. As such, the mausoleum is open for ziarah only on Fridays (Hari Jumat) coinciding with Pon, Kliwon or Pahing of the Javanese calendar. The shrine is open on three Fridays in any calendar month. On these days, ziarah visitation takes place at nights. Yayasan Sunan Kalijaga, the foundation in-charge of maintenance of the place organizes reading of the Suluk Linglung (the essence of Sunan Kalijaga's teachings) on Kliwon Jumat. Suluk Linglung is in Javanese. Each chapter of Suluk Linglung is chanted differently. The group chanting of Suluk Linglung is known as Waosan Suluk Linglung in Javanese. The chanting is led by Kadilangu villagers. Recitation of the Suluk Linglung is accompanied by Javanese music. The recitation lasts between 9 pm and midnight. Additionally, the shrine is open to ziarah during the Holy Month of Ramadhan. The Grebeg Besar festivities take place during the first ten days leading to Idul Adha. The Grebeg festivities commence at the Grand Mosque of Demak, leading up to Masjid Kadilangu. The Grebeg incorporates elements of pre-Islamic Javanese court rituals. In pre-Islamic Java, monarchs held Wilujen Gan Nagari or Royal Salvation Ceremonies for the well-being of the kingdom. Animals would be sacrificed to appease the deity. But Raden Patah, the first Sultan of Demak abolished the pre-Islamic custom. Between 1503-6, Java witnessed famine-like conditions. There were apprehensions that the natural calamities that afflicted Demak were related to abandonment of traditional customs (adat). Raden Patah approached Sunan Kalijaga for a solution. Sunan Kalijaga advised Raden Patah to sacrifice animals on the 10th of the Islamic month of Dzulhijah, a date that coincides with Idul Adha, in accordance with sharia (Islamic law). To attract more Javanese followers to Islam, Sunan Kalijaga played gamelan (traditional Javanese ensemble that is mostly played using percussive instruments) in the courtyard of the Kadilangu mosque. Grebeg Besar has continued from the turn of the sixteenth century to this day but has undergone modifications over time. In 1806, the Bupati or District Head of Demak Condronegoro VI introduced

modifications. The Grebeg festivities were interrupted during Japanese occupation of the Dutch East Indies (1942-45) but resumed soon after the occupation ended. The Grebeg festivity symbolizes the renewal of relationship between Sunan Kalijaga's descendants at Kadilangu village and the regent of Demak. On the eve of Idul Adha, pilgrims undertake ziarah to the grave of Sultan Bintoro of Demak, followed by visitation to the mausoleum of Sunan Kalijaga. On the eve of Idul Adha, Tumpeng (yellow rice that is shaped as a cone) is paraded from the alun-alun (town square) of Demak to the Great Mosque of Demak. The parade consists of 40 troops who bear torches. Pilgrims undertaking ziara and Demak locals participate in the parade as well, wearing black robes (the favorite color of Sunan Kalijaga). Tumpeng is distributed to residents, following prayers. There is scramble amongst pilgrims and Demak locals to get a share of the tumpeng. It is widely believed that consumption of the tumpeng guarantees health, prosperity, and barokah (favours) from Sunan Kalijaga. On the commencement of Idul Adha festivities, the saint's heirlooms, particularly Kris Kyai Crubuk (a kind of Javanese dagger in the saint's possession). There are elaborate heirloom rituals. The kris is ceremonially anointed with fragrant oils, specially prepared for the ritual by Kadilangu elders and the matriarch from Sunan Kalijaga's descendants. Participants undertaking the ritual must possess a clean heart and need to fast for forty days. On the day of Idul Adha, the Yayasan Sunan Kalijaga Foundation organizes a slametan (communal feast) consisting of tumpeng and side-dishes served on woven bamboo. The shrine is open on the first ten days of the Islamic month of Muharram. The 10th of Muharram is observed as the saint's death anniversary.

Reference: Saifudin, Mochamad. "Kidung Suluk Linglung Sunan Kalijaga Dibacakan Perdana". detikjateng, n.d.. <https://www.detik.com/jateng/budaya/d-6170204/kidung-suluk-linglung-sunan-kalijaga-dibacakan-perdana>.

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– Yes

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– Yes

↳ Birth

– Field doesn't know

↳ Transition to adulthood

– Yes

Notes: Circumcision ceremonies.

↳ Death

– Yes

Notes: Prayers for the soul of the deceased person by reciting select verses from the al-Quran when ziarah is undertaken.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Tumpeng Feast on Idul Adha sponsored by the Yayasan Sunan Kalijaga Foundation.

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– Yes

↳ Are these routes maintained together with the place:

– Yes

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Yes

↳ Priests

– No

↳ Local elites

– Yes

↳ Private contributions

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: n/a

– Other [specify]: The death anniversary of Sunan Kalijaga is observed on the 10th day of Muharram. Public recitation of select verses from the al-Quran.

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: Under the pendopo (Javanese-style pavilion) of the Kadilangu mosque).

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: Annual.

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

– Elites

– Non-elites

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: Field does not know. No data available.

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

– Elites

– Non-elites

– Religious professionals

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

↳ Incubation

– No

↳ Healing magic

– Yes

Notes: A relic well within the tomb complex, dating back to Sunan Kalijaga's times. The water from the well is believed to possess medicinal properties.

↳ Cleansing

– Yes

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:

– No

↳ Expiation

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Healing/Cleansing ritual held on the Islamic New Year coinciding with the First of Muharram; during the Islamic month of Rajab.

Notes: The descendants of Sunan Kalijaga organize the healing and cleansing rituals known as ruwatan (bi-annual rituals that coincide with Islamic New Year, the first of Muharram; and, during the month of Rajab). Ruwatan consists of a wayang kulit (Javanese puppet theater) performance. Guests are accommodated in the Notobraton Pendopo (a kind of village community hall). The message of the wayang kulit performances on both occasions is how to eliminate negativity and lead a purposeful life, reflected in the Javanese expression of hamurwo betorokolo. Sukarto is the chief wayang kulit protegy (a mentally disturbed person who needs to be healed) and is ritually represented in the wayang kulit by a shadow puppet tied with a rope. The wayang kulit performance and rituals commemorate Sunan Kalijaga's skill as a puppeteer. After the wayang performance during the month of Rajab, the puppeteer and the descendants of Sunan Kalijaga organize a thanksgiving procession, along with Sukarto, in Kadilangu village and subsequently cleanse themselves in perfumed water. Soon after the symbolic cleansing, the rope that was used to tie Sukarto is severed. On the Islamic New Year, coinciding with the First of Muharram, a mass feast for the public is organized in the pendopo of the Sunan Kalijaga mosque by the descendants of Sunan Kalijaga. For details on rituals enacted at the mausoleum of Sunan Kalijaga, see also <https://betanews.id/2023/02/rajab-jumlah-peziarah-di-makam-sunan-kalijaga-alami-peningkatan.html>

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

- ↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
 - specify: No data.
- ↳ How often do these rituals take place:
 - specify: Annual.
- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Majelis Ulema Indonesia or the Indonesian Ulema Council.
- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
 - No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

- ↳ Present full time
 - Yes

- ↳ Present part time
 - No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: The juru kunci is a male.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

Notes: Javanese.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Notes: The ritual exhibition of Sunan Kalijaga's possessions is undertaken only by the descendants of the saint. The preparation of aromatic oils used in the cleaning of the heirlooms of the saint is undertaken by post-menopausal women. The heirlooms are in turn, anointed with oil by the oldest female member from Sunan Kalijaga's descendants. All participants associated with the Grebeg rituals fast for 40 days to ensure that their mind is free from impurities.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: The Yayasan Sunan Kalijaga Foundation sponsors a pesantren (Javanese boarding house for religious instruction).

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: Yayasan Sunan Kalijaga (founded in 1963); Sunan Kalijaga's descendants. The district government of Demak and the village administration of Kadilangu under Indonesia's decentralized

administrative set-up also sponsor the Grebeg Besar festivities.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– Yes

Notes: The members of Yayasan Sunan Kalijaga are elected amidst the Kadilangu village community.

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

Notes: The descendants of Sunan Kalijaga were awarded the appellation of Pangeran Wijil that accorded them revenue from sawah (paddies) in Kadilangu village. The tax-exempt status was respected by the Dutch administration until ~ 1880.

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– No

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: Suluk Linglung consists of the recollection of Sunan Kalijaga's exploits and his philosophy. Part of the oral tradition. It was first penned down in the latter half of the nineteenth century at Surakarta.

Reference: Anom, Iman, Muhammad Kasri, and Kasmiran Sunadji. *Suluk Linglung Sunan Kalijaga (syeh Melayu) Karangannya*, Iman Anom Tahun 1806 Çaka/1884 Masehi Di Surakarta. Balai Pustaka, 1993.

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Evident in the enactment of the elaborate rituals.

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably the kyai (expert in Islam among the Javanese).

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– Yes

↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:

– No

↳ Housed within the place/structure:

– No

↳ As dedicatory inscription(s):

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Scriptures are present as a part of the oral tradition.

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https://www.google.co.in/books/edition/Java_Indonesia_and_Islam/kHb-640Gfa4C?hl=en&gbpv=1&dq=java,+indonesia+and+islam&printsec=frontcover.

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